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WP2 – Workshops on non-technical aspects

Summary Note

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This document requires the following approvals:

AUTHORISATION	Name	Signature	Date
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Executive summary

The following summarizes three workshops exploring the landscape of the interrelated non-technical challenges of CCUS (Carbon capture utilization and storage) hubs and clusters in Europe. The workshops were held to jointly with industries explore expert insights toward a strengthened shared understanding of both common as well as region-specific challenges experienced or expected on the path to developing CCUS hubs and clusters. This may serve to identify possible ways to cooperatively overcome such challenges and mobilize opportunities for carbon management in Europe toward net-zero emissions.

On May 2, 2023, the CCUS ZEN Horizon Project's the first workshop on non-technical challenges took place with attendees from various industries. Titled "Workshop on **legal and regulatory aspects**," the session featured a presentation by Lena Wammer Ostgaard, Legal Advisor at IOM Law followed by moderated discussion in breakout groups. The presentation focused on international and regional legal frameworks relevant to CCS operations, with an emphasis on the London Convention and Protocol, the Barcelona Convention, and the Helsinki Convention. Discussions during the workshop revolved around regulatory obstacles for hubs and clusters in various countries.

On June 14, 2023, the second workshop delved into key **economic and MRV/accounting issues** associated with CCUS implementation. The session featured presentations by Romain Viguier, Business Development Manager for Scottish Carbon Capture and Storage and Matthias Honegger of Perspectives Climate Research. Presentations examined the need for suitable business models, economic viability, infrastructure requirements, and competition with other decarbonization technologies. The significance of robust MRV mechanisms for tracking carbon dioxide in CCS projects and related challenges were explored – industry readiness, regulatory readiness, and limited recognition of certain activities under the EU ETS. Attendees from industries discussed with project partners.

On June 28, 2023, the third workshop of the CCUS ZEN Horizon Project's Work Package 2 focused on factors influencing social acceptance, political developments, and communication strategies. Florian Schmitt, of Perspectives Climate Research, moderated the event featuring presentations by Farid Karimi, Senior lecturer at the University of Jyväskylä, Darrick Evensen, Associate professor at the University of Edinburgh, and Ulrika Dahlberg, Researcher at the University of Jyväskylä. Presenters highlighted social acceptance challenges and explored key factors that influence it, such as risk/benefit perceptions, trust in stakeholders, communication and engagement strategies, and cultural orientations. The discussions with attendees from industry explored how these issues could affect development of hubs and clusters and identified potential solutions. Participants shared experiences and insights including regarding social acceptance and political support, as well as a wide range of factors affecting acceptance.

For more detailed information on the workshops, including the presenters' slides and an in-depth study of non-technical challenges refer to the resources provided for CCUS ZEN Partners and Network Partners on the CCUS ZEN sharepoint as well as any resources available on the CCUS ZEN project website or contact project partners.

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LEGAL AND REGULATORY ASPECTS

1. General Information on the first workshop

On Tuesday, May 2, 2023, the project partners of Work Package WP2 of the Horizon Project CCUS ZEN held their first of three workshops with attendees from various industries to explore the landscape of interrelated non-technical challenges for CCUS. The workshop series sought to strengthen shared understanding of common (and specific) challenges experienced or expected on the path to developing CCUS hubs and clusters and point to possible ways to overcome them.

The first workshop was titled 'Workshop on legal and regulatory aspects' and included a presentation by Lena Wammer Ostgaard, Legal Advisor at IOM Law, and moderated discussion (moderated by Matthias Honegger, Head of Carbon *Dioxide Removals* at Perspectives Climate Research).

Following the presentation focussed on international and regional instruments breakout discussions examined a wide range of legal and regulatory challenges for hub- and cluster development. The discussions brought to light various reflections and reactions of experts and practitioners on regulatory and legal shortcomings.

The presentation slide deck by Lena Wammer Ostgaard, Legal Advisor at IOM Law is found on the [project website here](#).

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1.1 Presentation

International, regional, and national legal frameworks form part of the starting point when identifying value chains, for example, by dictating whether and where storage may occur and by setting criteria for the transboundary transport and storage of CO₂. The presentation considered some of the international and regional instruments that are particularly relevant for the two regions included in the study, namely the 1972 Convention on the Prevention of Marine Pollution by Dumping of Wastes and Other Matter (London Convention) and its 1996 Protocol (London Protocol), the 1995 Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean (Barcelona Convention) and the 1992 Convention on the Protection of the Marine Environment of the Baltic Sea (Helsinki Convention). These instruments are only applicable to offshore storage, not onshore. Thus, the presentation considered the implications these instruments can have for cross-border transportation and offshore storage of CO₂. Onshore storage and “utilization” were outside the scope of the presentation but will be considered in the white paper.

London Protocol

As of today, the London Protocol represents the most advanced international regulatory instrument addressing the storage of CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formations. While storage of CO₂ was initially prohibited under the Protocol, the Protocol was amended in 2006 to allow for storage of CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formation, simultaneously setting out criteria for this to occur. This created a legal basis in international environmental law to regulate storage of CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formations. The London Protocol has since been amended to overcome another barrier – the export prohibition in article 6. The amendment is still not in force at the time of writing, awaiting a sufficient number of ratifications. After ten years in limbo, the Contracting Parties agreed to an interim solution of provisional application which became effective through the 2019 Resolution. As such, Contracting Parties are now free to export CO₂ for the purpose of storage across borders provided that certain criteria have been met, including the need for an arrangement or agreement that confirms and allocates permitting responsibilities.

There are four regional sea conventions in Europe. For the purpose of CCUS ZEN, the Helsinki Convention and Barcelona Convention are particularly relevant, covering the Baltic Sea and the Mediterranean Sea, respectively. These conventions are similar to the London Convention and Protocol, and seek to, among other things, prevent pollution of the marine environment caused by dumping of wastes or other matter in their respective areas.

Helsinki Convention

The Helsinki Convention bans the dumping of all wastes and other matter with the exception of dredged material (art. 11), which in each case requires a prior special permit. Thus, as CO₂ is not listed as an exception, storage in the Convention area (Baltic Sea) is prohibited. It is important to highlight the Helsinki Commission’s position that “the Convention is amended

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whenever deemed necessary, such as to follow the developments in international environmental and maritime laws.”¹

There are clear developments, both in the region and internationally, to facilitate and regulate storage of CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formation. Examples include the amendments made to the London Protocol and the 1992 Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR) in 2007. The amendment made to the OSPAR Convention is similar to the 2006 amendment to the London Protocol as it added CO₂ to the list of wastes or other matter that may be considered for dumping.² Thus, while the storage of CO₂ is prohibited under the Helsinki Convention today, this could change in the future.

Barcelona Convention

The Convention for the Protection of the Mediterranean Sea Against Pollution was initially adopted in 1976 and entered into force in 1978. In 1995, the Convention was renamed and amended to encompass the key concepts adopted at the 1992 Rio Conference and to include coasts in its scope (renamed the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment and the Coastal Region of the Mediterranean – Barcelona Convention). The Barcelona Convention presents a more unique case when considering whether or not it facilitates offshore storage as it has two dumping protocols.

The first dumping protocol was adopted in 1976 and entered into force in 1978 in line with the original Convention. This protocol follows the London Convention’s “black-and grey-list” approach, listing the wastes or other matter that are prohibited to dump in one annex (Annex I) and the wastes or other matter that may be considered for dumping in another annex (Annex II). All other wastes or other matter not listed may be dumped pursuant to a general permit. As CO₂ is not listed in either of the two annexes, it may be considered for dumping having first acquired a general permit.

The 1976 dumping protocol was also amended in 1995 to follow the developments of the London Convention. The amended protocol is more similar to the London Protocol and implements the “reverse-list approach” which implies that all dumping is prohibited except for the wastes or other matter explicitly listed in the protocol. CO₂ is not included on the list, which would imply that it is prohibited to dump.

The 1995 protocol is not yet in force. This implies that the original protocol from 1976 applies, which could allow for the storage of CO₂ under a general permit. That said, this interpretation may not be straight forward, as the Contracting Parties that have accepted the amended protocol are generally bound by certain obligations under the 1969 Vienna Convention on the Law of Treaties not to defeat the object and purpose of a treaty prior to its entry into force. IOM Law will provide a more detailed analysis on this in the white paper, but their preliminary observations suggest that storing CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formations would not necessarily defeat the object and purpose of the protocol. It can be observed that

¹ HELCOM, ‘*The Helsinki Convention*’ <<https://helcom.fi/about-us/convention/>> accessed 11.05.2023.

² Amendments were made to Annex II and III.

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regardless of the interpretation, there is not a framework in place in the Convention itself that regulates and facilitates the storage of CO₂ in sub-seabed geological formations as of yet.

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1.2 Moderated Discussion

Participants discussed the following guiding questions and related pertinent observations:

- A. What legal or regulatory obstacles have you encountered, or do you expect (in your role)?
- B. How will contracts between various actors in CCUS hubs/clusters need to clarify roles, responsibilities, ownership, liability, and other such aspects?
- C. Which actor needs to take action for overcoming specific obstacles (and how)?

Descriptions of Issues Encountered or Expected (and possible steps to overcome)

EU CCS Directive related issues

- Liability issues - private sector / storage of CO₂ / issues with handover period to government (operational costs)
- Challenges with cross-border shared projects, who owns CO₂? Also relevant to national projects?
- Policy perspectives - regulatory frameworks. Policy alignment overall. Potential financial incentives
- Issues where there are little or no incentives for biogenic / DAC

Issues related to a domestic regulatory framework suitable for CCUS

- Development of national, regional, and municipal framework
- Incentivise local communities and social acceptance
- National Governments need to take action
- Engage more with NGOs, especially around surveys, public, and social acceptance
- Industry needs to lead the way (taking action). NGOs need to be involved; knowledge-sharing important to avoid confusion (i.e., comparing with fracking)
- In Baltic states – since 2019 there is a ban against ANY CCS activity (research and storage). Without a permissible framework it is basically impossible to move ahead on storage of any kind. Meetings have been held, but there is little dedicated effort to overturn the ban. In Latvia and Poland new legal frameworks that are permissible are being developed. Difficult to put a timeframe on it.
- In Lithuania Parliament was very favorable, but then there was public rejection and consequently the ban was introduced. Public perception is unfavorable. Successful countries have long history of mining and fossil fuel extraction; easier discussion there.
- Fertilizer industry (3-4Mio tCO₂) has started with capture facility (15kt ca) – different discussion to some extent. More focus on capture could be helpful in steering public perception.
- DACCS and BECCS offer an opportunity to alter the debates on CCS – at the end might allow to accelerate engagement of stakeholders. Not a competition between removals and storage. Do the oil and gas companies need to be a part of the solutions?

Permitting issues (local or national permitting for storage, transport infrastructure etc.)

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- Local v. regional permits
- France: permit process takes time (1.5-2 years for the administration to examine the demand)
- Permitting huge problem in Belgium: Huge installations that need permitting. Pace of processes are inadequate.
- In Denmark there was administrative uncertainty – which office is in charge? For onshore it has not yet been decided which authority it is.
- Acceleration of permitting on renewables – will also be valid for CO₂ projects.
- In various MS administrations – sometimes it is the one in charge of Energy, Mines, Environmental issues. Different parallel conversations. Same challenge in US.
- EU Commission could put out timelines on who should be responsible at which stage? Guidance or time limit (as part of the CCS Directive operationalization process) to MS administrations.

Contractual issues (e.g., between capture, transport, storage, utilizing actors)

- Challenges at storage sites, who is responsible? You need to have regulation.
- How do you keep costs, liabilities, and pricing in a successful business model?
- Intermittency
- Third-party access
- Ownership to CO₂ throughout the value chain
- Financial incentives, such as ETS
- France: industries interested by CCS, but the liability of the operator is a barrier, especially for storage, and on the long-term, before transfer to the State
- Commercial agreements: Lots of discussion between capturing and storing entities; need lots of time to see these mature. Both sides need to make investment decisions at the same time. We need customers at the time of developing storage sites. This is the main issue to launch investment. Norway has taken part of the risk by committing the storage of two emitters to ensure a minimum volume of storage allowing to scale the Longship project.
- Some initiatives for contracts between aggregators and storage developers; part of the risk being taken by the aggregator or cluster developer.
- Many clusters do not sufficiently examine the ownership of stored CO₂ – requiring many disparate contracts. An aggregator allows simplified contracting. Too much separation of consortium vs. storage provider.
- An aggregator accommodating CO₂ from various countries requirements vis a vis international agreements are increasing! Also, a difference between point-to-point vs. multi-source, and multi storage sites.
- Capturers are first in line in case of disruptions of the storage chain - in case of delay etc. capturer is most immediately touched (given that ETS is ultimate revenue source); some guarantee of future ETS exemption once the chain is approved would be required for sufficient certainty (even if there is delay in the chain). → Full chain cannot really be guaranteed, only if the capturer allows. Could there be a national or EU fund / guarantee?
- In case of Longship storage is well on track, yet capture projects are delayed...

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Others

- France: high investments are required for reservoir characterisation, with uncertainties on the result, so industries hesitate to go for CCS. The State could have the role to incentivise the geological research.

1.3 Key findings from the workshop on legal and regulatory issues

International and regional instruments play an important role when identifying locations for value chains. It does so by prescribing a legal framework with specific and general requirements that Contracting Parties must abide by (and thus operators where the instruments have been implemented into national laws). The example of the Helsinki Convention also prohibits offshore storage in the Convention area, demonstrating that such regional conventions can determine where and if one can store CO₂. Findings from the legal sub-task will be presented in detail in the White Paper and used by WP 3 in identifying locations for value chains.

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2 General Information on the second workshop

On Wednesday, June 14, 2023, the project partners of Work Package WP2 of the Horizon Project CCUS ZEN held their second of three workshops with attendees from various industries on mapping non-technical aspects. It was titled 'Workshop on Economic, MRV, and Accounting Issues' and included presentations by Romain F H Viguiet, Business Development & Project Manager at Scottish Carbon Capture and Storage (SCCS), and Matthias Honegger, Senior Research Associate at Perspectives Climate Research.

A presentation focusing on economic issues such as the development of business models, and among others, the interaction with additional decarbonisation technologies was followed by a presentation on MRV and accounting aspects, highlighting the main issues that arise in this area and the challenges to be derived from this. Workshop discussions were held on these topics, focusing on particular issues related to hubs and clusters. The aim was to learn from a group of experts how they assess these obstacles and problems, which of them they have already encountered, and how these obstacles can be overcome.

Presentation Slide Decks

The presentations by Romain F H Viguiet, Business Development Manager at Scottish Carbon Capture and Storage (SCCS) and Matthias Honegger, Senior Research Associate at Perspectives Climate Research are found on the [project website here](#).

2.1 Presentation on Economics

Why focus on Economics? When you learn about the set of technologies that form part of CCUS and about the potential that CCUS offers in term of decarbonising industry and the economy, you might ask yourself: why has CCUS not been already deployed globally?

There is clearly a lack of incentives to encourage companies to invest in CCS, no clear regulatory framework for the development of CCS and a lack of public awareness of CCS technologies – most people don't know about CCS and it's potential as a climate change mitigation solution. But for the long-term sustainability of the CCS sector itself it appears that economic issues are the main obstacles.

The cost of capturing, transporting, and storing carbon dioxide is still high and not yet economically viable for many industries. In addition to the operating cost of CCS, significant investment is required to establish a suitable infrastructure for CCS. The development of CCS at scale requires transport infrastructure such as port facilities, CO₂ pipelines, collection hubs, etc. In addition, the limited availability of suitable storage facilities at proximity to emission sources is also a major constraint on the development of CCS in Europe

The project is identifying and examining possible incentives and disincentives for investments from private and public sectors in CCS and this workshop was organised to

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discuss the key elements (to financial risk assessment) that would likely be involved in CCUS investment decision and consider other economic aspects such as those related to infrastructure needs at local and regional levels for CCUS Hubs, Industry clusters, and CCUS value chains.

The project initial mapping exercise with networking partners and project partners based in the regions of interest helped identify many issues that were then organised into 5 main issue headings.

Many identified issues were overlapping with legal, political, policy, or social. We also considered the issues not covered under the legal, or political, or public awareness chapter, that a potential investor in CCUS would have to consider.

Business Model

The responses collected highlight the criticality of establishing a suitable business model to ensure the long-term sustainability of the CCUS sector. It is widely recognized that the sector needs to develop business models that incentivize investment in CCS infrastructure. Unlike traditional product-based industries, CCS operates as a service, specifically a waste management service, and therefore requires government intervention to attach liability to CO₂ emissions and acknowledge the value of capture and sequestration activities. While various approaches have their merits, no country has yet discovered a business model that effectively drives long-term investment in CCS.

Additional issues associated with the business model were identified during the data collection process. For instance, mitigating and underwriting cross-chain risks, which are particularly high for first-of-a-kind projects, necessitates special support within the business model. Financial security is another essential aspect to underwrite CO₂ storage permits. It is crucial to develop a comprehensive framework that addresses both supply and demand aspects of the CCUS sector. Additionally, the business model must account for the risk of carbon leakage resulting from emissions standards or a high carbon price, such as the EU ETS. One potential mitigating mechanism under development by the European Commission is the implementation of a carbon border adjustment mechanism (CBAM).

Interaction with other decarbonisation technologies

The survey responses also shed light on the interaction between CCS and other decarbonization technologies. CCS is just one of the potential solutions for decarbonizing the industry, and it is essential to assess how the development of alternative technologies may impact or support CCS advancement. Major CCUS projects, along with other net-zero-aligned initiatives like renewable energy, hydrogen infrastructure, and oil and gas decommissioning, will be concurrently developed. Consequently, investments in one sector can potentially influence another, either positively or negatively. Resource allocation, funding availability, and competition for skilled workers are key factors to consider. Long-term strategic planning is vital to ensure all necessary activities to achieve net-zero targets can be effectively executed. Questions arise regarding the availability of fabrication capacity and skilled workers specifically for CCUS, the sufficiency of clean energy for processes such as CO₂ utilization, and the sequencing and timing of large-scale projects. Additionally, it is important to address the potential need for worker retraining or sector transitioning to enable a just and smooth transition process.

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Complexity of the CCUS value chain

The responses further highlighted the complexity of the CCUS value chain, encompassing capture, transport, storage, and utilization. This complexity necessitates the involvement of multiple organizations and introduces uncertainties at each stage. Cross-chain risks emerge between different stages of the CCS chain, requiring careful management and coordination. In CCUS clusters, where multiple organizations are involved, the complexity and number of parties that need to reach agreements can compound these cross-chain risks.

Marine and land use planning

Several responses emphasized the importance of marine and land use planning and its impact on the deployment of CCS. The nature of planning in these areas can either support or hinder CCS implementation. Limited experience with CO₂ storage sites and related infrastructure introduces significant uncertainties. Additionally, competing uses of marine space and land, such as offshore wind, fishing, leisure activities, and nature conservation, must be considered and balanced effectively. Collaboration between onshore planning authorities may be necessary, especially for cross-border infrastructure projects. It is essential to provide reassurance to investors that planners and regulators possess the knowledge and expertise to handle new developments. Capacity building and training programs for planners and regulators should be established to ensure they can effectively manage the entire CCUS value chain. Insufficient capacity and knowledge can lead to delays, impacting the economic viability and attractiveness of CCUS projects. Long and complex planning applications can result in extended timelines, jeopardizing the viability of partnerships and collaborations.

Ambiguities in long-term storage liability

Another significant issue highlighted in the responses pertains to the uncertainty and ambiguity surrounding long-term storage liability in CCS. According to the CO₂ Storage Directive, responsibility for a CO₂ storage site can be transferred from the operator to the competent authority at some point after closure, typically a minimum of 20 years, as determined by the competent authority. However, the operationalisation of the storage directive differs among Member States, leading to economic uncertainties, particularly in cases of bankruptcies that occur before the transfer to national authorities. Storage operators are required to provide financial security, or an equivalent mechanism determined by the competent authority, to fulfil all obligations under the directive. This includes addressing any leaks and the surrendering of EU ETS emissions trading allowances for any escaped CO₂. Ambiguities in permitting processes and the valuation or costing of liability introduce economic challenges that can impact the viability of CCS projects. Defining appropriate methodologies to value and cost the liability remains an unresolved aspect in this context.

2.2 Presentation on MRV and Accounting issues

CCUS has emerged as one of the promising solutions to reduce or remove carbon dioxide emissions. To ensure its effectiveness and credibility, robust monitoring, reporting and verification (MRV) systems and accounting practices are essential. Without effective MRV, it is not possible to accurately measure and verify the amount of carbon dioxide captured, transported, stored or used. And without clear accounting rules, the mitigation outcomes

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realised with CCUS cannot be properly reflected in greenhouse gas inventories. Hence, MRV and accounting serve as the bedrock for transparency, accountability, and trust in CCUS projects.

The presentation highlighted the significance of MRV and accounting for CCUS and aimed to provide a comprehensive overview of both issues. The presentation addressed several key points and challenges related to MRV, namely readiness of industry practitioners, ongoing VCS methodology development, best practices for MRV, varying operationalisation of the CCS Directive, the role of the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework, liability and penalties for leaks and disturbances, readiness of the national GHG inventory responsible office, reporting negative emissions, and recognition of negative emissions in the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS).

Readiness of Industry Practitioners:

MRV is essential for carbon markets and results-based climate policies to track mitigation outcomes. Project developers must provide detailed monitoring, reporting, and verification of their emissions reductions or removals. Specific methodologies must be applied to determine what to monitor and calculate.

Industry practitioners face several challenges when it comes to MRV readiness. Firstly, requirements for MRV may differ depending on carbon market standards and the types of CCUS activities with different specific guidelines and protocols in place. Secondly, the readiness of industry practitioners is uncertain, particularly for those who have no prior experience or participation in baseline-and-credit markets. Implementing effective MRV systems requires expertise, technical capacity, and familiarity with the methodologies and reporting frameworks specific to CCUS projects.

Ongoing VCS Methodology Development:

By now, there has not been a comprehensive set of methodologies available for various CCUS projects to access voluntary carbon markets and generate carbon revenue. Those methodologies that are available to date are limited in terms of geographical scope or eligible CCUS activities. A noteworthy exception from this is the so-called CCS+ initiative, a private-sector driven initiative that is currently developing a comprehensive methodological framework under Verra's Verified Carbon Standard (VCS) for the full suite of CCUS activities. It is important to note that limited experience with carbon market MRV among CCUS stakeholders may pose challenges. Efforts are being made to bridge this gap and build capacity among practitioners to effectively implement the developed methodologies. These issues highlight the need for clear guidelines, international cooperation, and consistent implementation to ensure the integrity and effectiveness of MRV and accounting in CCUS activities.

Unclear Best Practices for MRV:

Currently, there is no internationally harmonized and adopted MRV framework specific to CCUS initiatives. The lack of clear best practices for MRV in the context of CCUS projects is a significant challenge. This arises from the diversity of carbon market types and standards. Each carbon market may have its own specific requirements and guidelines for MRV, resulting in a lack of standardized approaches. Moreover, the available methodologies for MRV differ in terms of their quality, with a trade-off between environmental integrity and practicality. Some

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methodologies may prioritize rigor and accuracy, while others focus on simplicity and feasibility. This contributes to low trust in the environmental integrity of CCUS activities.

Varying Operationalization of the CCS Directive:

The varying level of operationalisation of the CCS Directive poses challenges in achieving consistent MRV practices among EU member states and can cause inconsistencies in tracking carbon flows. Efforts should be made to align national legislation with the common monitoring and reporting standards outlined in the Directive to ensure coherence, transparency, and comparability of CCS activities across borders. This harmonisation is crucial for promoting the success and credibility of CCS initiatives within the EU.

Role of the EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework:

The EU Carbon Removal Certification Framework (CRCF) is going to provide a certification system for carbon removal projects in the EU and has the potential to become a revenue source for CCUS projects in the long term.

Challenges include the definition of the framework's scope, uncertainty regarding its integration into the overall EU policy landscape, and potential disregard by voluntary carbon markets or domestic policies.

Liability and Penalties for Leaks and Disturbances:

The issue of liability and ownership of CO₂ assets becomes more complex in storage and utilization hubs and clusters, where CO₂ from multiple sources is processed or stored. The storage operator may be liable for leakage from the storage site, and agreements between the storage provider and CO₂ suppliers could include sharing associated financial risks.

Clear attribution rules are necessary to establish a fair distribution of liabilities in such scenarios and clarity on the treatment of physical CO₂ leakage in national legislation and permitting conditions is needed. The EU CCS Directive provides some guidance and also carbon market standard setters have developed instruments to regulate financial harm from leakage.

Readiness of the National GHG Inventory Responsible Entity:

Accurate and transparent greenhouse gas (GHG) inventories at the national level are crucial for tracking emissions reduction targets and informing climate policy decisions.

Challenges include assessing whether national agencies responsible for reporting GHG inventories to the UNFCCC are equipped to track novel forms of climate mitigation, including CCUS. This readiness entails having the necessary technical expertise, methodologies, and systems in place to accurately measure and account for CCUS-related emissions and removals.

Lack of Clarity in Reporting Negative Emissions:

Including removals in national GHG inventory reporting is important for transparency and creating incentives for pursuing negative emissions technologies.

The lack of clarity in reporting negative emissions from CO₂ removals from novel technologies poses challenges in accurately accounting for the removals achieved through these

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approaches. Ensuring transparent and consistent reporting could enable proper recognition of and encourage investment in capturing and storing e.g., biogenic CO₂ emissions.

Unclear Recognition of Negative Emissions in EU Emissions Trading System (ETS):

The EU ETS is a cap-and-trade mechanism designed to reduce GHG emissions in the EU. Currently, there is a lack of clarity regarding the inclusion and treatment of negative emissions from CCS technologies, such as bioenergy with CCS (BECCS) and direct air capture with CCS (DACCS), in the EU ETS. Revisions are needed to recognize "carbon-neutral" CO₂ capture and storage from technologies like BECCS and DACCS as "negative emissions" and thus incentivize such projects. It remains unclear if inclusion is desired or if indirect incentives will be generated through the CRCF.

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2.3 Moderated discussion on Economics and MRV & Accounting

Participants discussed the following guiding questions and related pertinent observations:

Economic issues

- A. How problematic will the economic issues presented be in specific countries (give examples)?
- B. How (policy incentives, market driven, or both) will/should the business case for CCUS hubs/clusters come about?
- C. Which economic actor needs to take action for overcoming specific obstacles (give country-specific examples)?
- D. What is the game plan to get going? Role of (local) authorities, market response, industry...

MRV and Accounting issues

- E. How problematic will the MRV and accounting issues presented be in specific countries (give examples)?
- F. How can actors build capacity for MRV and proper accounting?
- G. Which actor needs to take action for overcoming MRV obstacles (and how)?

The following table provides an overview of issues noted during the discussion.

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How do Economic challenges pertain to specific actors (please indicate which country)?

<i>Challenges</i>	<i>Actor types</i>					
	Industry actors capturing CO ₂	Transport service providers	Storage service providers	Local government	National Government	3rd party verifiers
<i>Business model</i>	growing cost due to ETS (but not sufficient for storage investments)	cost needs to come down (perhaps 50%) both in capture and transport compared to US: tax-credits create cost-recovery	exploration risks are a challenge in CCS, (usually compensated by a cost recovery mechanism in oil & gas) revenue streams are uncertain: CO ₂ trading prices do not make CCS model sustainable without a CO ₂ price floor		geological surveys by public too slow! need to achieve somehow a de facto carbon price floor (carbon contracts for difference?)	
<i>Interaction with other decarbonisation technologies</i>	fuel switch or efficiency – often cheaper than CCUS hydrogen could also enter the picture medium-term		"competition" between utilisation and storage			
<i>Complexity of the CCUS value chain</i>		proximity matters to lower cost who is the driver / owner of CCUS? control over carbon revenues?	CCS suffers from high oil prices to access services need more competition in storage-market			
<i>Marine and land use planning</i>						
<i>Long-term storage liability</i>						
<i>Other</i>						

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How do MRV and accounting challenges pertain to specific actors (please indicate which country)?

Actor types

<i>Challenges</i>	Industry actors capturing CO₂	Transport service providers	Storage service providers	National Government	3rd party verifiers
<i>Proper application of MRV methodologies by CCUS value-chain participants</i>				not much focus on MRV (except long-term monitoring for leakage) in Denmark	
<i>Successful verification by third parties</i>			Lack of guidelines creates uncertainty, making economic case too conservative: the transfer points are not numerous and can be monitored, release point can have a seal		
<i>Proper reporting to national GHG Inventory administrators (e.g., by CCUS operators)</i>	Accounting not yet seen as a pressing problem, other issues more pressing right now (like economic business model)				
<i>Proper GHG Inventory updating by national agency tasked with Inventory Reporting</i>					
<i>Challenges with long term monitoring (potentially beyond crediting period)</i>			High focus from governments but small pb: CCS operators are coming up with technical for long term monitoring: VSP, plum modelisation		
<i>Other Challenges in MRV and accounting</i>				are trade associations a precondition for successfully lobbying for government action?	MRV has been difficult to do in international standards making. It is unclear how important this will be though.

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2.4 Key Takeaways on Economics and MRV & Accounting

Please note that the workshop was attended primarily by actors representing industry, whereas CO₂ storage and transport sector actors were underrepresented. The findings listed in the following thus may reflect for this and lack some relevant insights from practitioners in the areas of CO₂ transport and storage.

Economic:

- Fuel switching and efficiency enhancements remain highly attractive and relevant first steps towards decarbonisation. Hydrogen could also become increasingly relevant if prices and availability develop favorably.
- Allowance prices under the EU ETS are increasing, thus enhancing attractiveness of CCUS, but the cost of capturing CO₂ remains too high in the absence of additional incentivization or dedicated funding. There is thus a need for capture cost to come down for the operating cost of CCS to become manageable.
- Mature, available storage sites are geographically often far from clustered industries: in some cases cost of transport may match the cost of capture. Clustered industries may need local storage solutions to lower cost.
- With the small number of mature storage sites there may be risks of (perceived) price-fixing and oligopoly behavior among storage operators, which would artificially keep storage prices high. CCS will benefit from more competition amongst storage services.
- For the storage service providers, cost associated with exploration poses an investment risk, which may require dedicated public funding support.

MRV & Accounting:

- Storage service providers face challenges in successful third-party verification due to lack of guidelines, leading to economic conservatism. Transfer points can be monitored, and release points can have seals.
- Industry actors prioritize other pressing issues over MRV and accounting, such as the economic business model.
- In Denmark, the national government has limited focus on MRV, except for long-term monitoring of leakage.

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3 General information on the third workshop

On Wednesday, June 28, 2023, the project partners of Work Package (WP) 2 of the Horizon Project CCUS ZEN held the last of three workshops on mapping non-technical aspects with attendees from various industries. The workshop 'Socio-political Issues' was moderated by Florian Schmitt, Junior Carbon Consultant at Perspectives Climate Research. The event included a presentation by Farid Karimi, Senior lecturer at University of Jyväskylä, Darrick Evensen, Associate professor at University of Edinburgh and Ulrika Dahlberg, Researcher at University of Jyväskylä

The focus of the presentation was on the factors that influence social acceptance, such as risk/benefit perceptions, trust in stakeholders, communication and engagement from prospective projects, and cultural orientation, as well as the current political development of CCS. Workshop discussions were then held on these topics, focusing on issues related to hubs and clusters. The aim was to discover, from a group of experts, how they have experienced issues of socio-political acceptance and communication in relation to CCUS, and how they assess the factors affecting acceptance and obstacles to acceptance. We discussed which of the factors they have already encountered, and how they can possibly be overcome.

Presenters

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The presentation slide deck on socio-political issues is found on the [project website here](#).

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3.1 Presentation on socio-political issues

Social acceptance

Lack of social acceptance has hindered the deployment of CCS on a large scale, for example in Germany and the Netherlands. Most laypeople do not reflect on how industry should be decarbonised, and are not very familiar with the technology, and the differences between CCS, CCU, CCUS and BECCS. However, public understanding has been increasing slowly during the last two decades. There is potential for targeted communication, bearing in mind that more knowledge does not always mean more acceptance.

Commonly perceived risks of CCS are related to uncertainty of the technology, high costs of deployment, rising costs of products and reduced incentives to mitigate carbon emissions or address causes of the emissions. Also, concerns over the safety of transportation of CO₂, leakage or induced seismicity at the storage locations are common. Regulation and monitoring of the processes are in some cases feared to be inadequate. Perceived benefits are emissions reduction from industries and from power production, jobs creation, job preservation, and CCS being part of a net-zero solution. Benefit perceptions are more important for acceptance of CCS generally, and risk perceptions more important for acceptance of specific local projects. Low benefit perception also increases risk perception. In other words, if the benefits are not seen as remarkable, the risks get more emphasised. When local opposition towards CCS occurs, this is often called NIMBY (Not in My Backyard), meaning acceptance of the process generally, but out of sight and not in one's own residential area. This may, however, be a too simplistic description of the resistance, as there are more nuanced reasons to it.

CCU is more commonly accepted than CCS. Acceptance also varies according to the source of emission. BECCS is generally more supported than CCS. There is some equivocal evidence of more support for CCUS projects if emissions come from industrial sources, compared to power plants. Direct air capture has proven to be hard to understand and appears futuristic or raises concern about energy requirements. Additional information about DACCS has even decreased support. Support for DACCS onshore is higher than offshore, which proves that projects far away do not automatically get more support.

Trust in stakeholders is one factor affecting risk perception and acceptance of new technologies including CCS. Trust in research and academic sectors and NGOs is consistently higher: the public relies on what they advocate or verify and prefers to involve with them in decision-making processes. Trust in governments and industry is generally high in the Nordic countries and lower in the Mediterranean countries. Another explaining factor to regional differences in social acceptance is cultural differences. They affect both experts and laypeople to some extent.

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Social acceptability

While *social acceptance* is a more passive top-down process, *social acceptability* means active support of public in combination with acceptance. Therefore, social acceptability is a more democratic and socially inclusive concept, pertaining to engagement of local communities in developing CC(U)S projects.

To keep the whole process of implementation of CCUS projects democratic and inclusive, the public needs to be involved at the earliest stages of planning before key decisions are made. The communication process should be two-way, including multiple approaches, such as focus groups, public broadcasting, deliberative workshops, working with traditional media, adept use of social media, and accessible and relevant websites. Concerning the content and style of communication, the local context matters: e.g., the landscape, socio-economic setting, employment trends, education levels, but also the context in which CCUS is discussed. Communicating the full range of risks and benefits, risk mitigation, values, trade-offs, narratives, and facts has a positive effect on how CCUS projects are received by the public.

Political development

Two main factors have been changing the political landscape vis-à-vis CC(U)S in Europe are meeting the EU climate goals and Russian invasion of Ukraine. CCS is increasingly seen as an option to secure energy supply from undesired alternatives like fossil fuels for the short-term, and from biomass, while curbing CO₂ emissions in order to meet the ambitious climate goals. Political will and policies that are favourable to CCUS eventually affect social acceptance, especially in regions where the dialogue between the authorities and the public is on a good basis.

Public acceptance and political development country wise

A table with assessment of public acceptance and political development in the countries of the Baltic Sea Region and Mediterranean region was presented. The table is based on a literature analysis of recent scientific articles about social and political aspects of CCUS. Three parameters were chosen for public acceptance: high, medium, and low (although no country was identified as high in acceptance), and three for political development: favourable, business as usual, and unfavourable, where business as usual means no change due to the Russian war in Ukraine or EU climate goals. There are no remarkable differences to be seen between the Baltic Sea and Mediterranean countries. The most interesting countries for further research could be those with low cohesion between social acceptance and the political development, such as France and Poland, where public acceptance is low and political development favourable. Obviously, the situation in each country is not static, and especially political development can move quite rapidly in different directions. This table, however, represents our subjective interpretation of existing literature and current development. The data will be used to make maps where countries are colour coded according to their state of development regarding CCUS.

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Regions: Baltic Sea & Mediterranean

COUNTRY	PUBLIC ACCEPTANCE	POLITICAL DEVELOPMENT
Denmark (BAL)	Medium	Favorable
Estonia (BAL)	Medium	Business as usual
Finland (BAL)	Medium	Business as usual
Germany (BAL)	Low	Business as usual
Latvia (BAL)	Medium	Business as usual
Lithuania (BAL)	Low	Unfavorable
Poland (BAL)	Low	Favorable
Sweden (BAL)	Medium	Favorable
France (MED)	Low	Favorable
Greece (MED)	Low	Business as usual
Italy (MED)	Low	Unfavorable
Spain (MED)	Medium	Business as usual
Turkey (MED)	Medium	Business as usual

3.2 Discussion of Socio-Political Challenges

Participants discussed the following guiding questions and related pertinent observations:

- A. Have you encountered resistance or support concerning CCUS in your projects/region?
- B. Which actors should be responsible for communication about CCUS?
- C. What should be the aim of communication (more knowledge/acceptance/active support and involvement)?
- D. What political developments do you perceive as the most important for, or constraining of, CC(U)S development?

Key points of discussion

The breakout room discussions generally supported the statement that trust in governments and industry is higher in the Nordic countries than in the Mediterranean countries. This affects the implementation of CC(U)S projects and defines who should do the communication and how. Examples from Denmark show that high trust in the government makes communication (relatively) easy and that information has a positive effect on acceptance. Municipalities, local politicians, and companies are involved in outreach and communication with the locals. However, there are micro-cultural differences between northern and southern parts of the country, which affect acceptance, and a city-countryside polarisation, where the countryside is reluctant to “take garbage from others”. Perceived risks by the public are health issues, or even the risk of death because of CO₂ leakages and accidents, decreased property value, and regarding offshore CCS, a negative impact on the ocean scenery and fishery. In general, the Danish example of mobilising local politicians to

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communicate and engage with local communities has gone well and built trust between stakeholders. Therefore, there are some lessons here to be learnt for other countries.

In Germany, there has been communication from the Ministry for Economic Affairs and Climate Action about decarbonisation of industry through CC(U)S, and there has been a shift in the political position towards CCS for achieving climate goals. Tendency towards applying CCUS in industry, particularly cement, is increasing, as there are no other viable options to mitigate CO₂ emission otherwise. The chemical industry in Germany sees CO₂ as a valuable product for utilising rather than waste.

In Poland, there is little knowledge about CC(U)S among the public, and local resistance against onshore CCS is high. Members of the public perceived CCS as a trick by the energy companies to continue using coal. However, the cement and steel industries are interested in CCS.

In France, mistrust towards the state and the emitting industries is high. As a result, the public oppose CCS projects as a part of opposing the government. Companies are afraid of public reactions and therefore communicate CCS projects to local populations later than best practice would recommend (e.g., first notice in mass media). Trust in research organisations and NGOs is, on the other hand, high, and information from them is received well. Therefore, NGOs and experts should be responsible for communication.

In Spain there has been success in early engagement and setting up regional committees for sharing knowledge and experience. But the general public in Spain has a reticence to accept CCUS – perhaps due to experience previously with fracking.

Communication and the implementation of new projects was also discussed in general (beyond specific countries): the role of social media having potential to influence project support on a local level, and the importance of explaining extant regulations and in that way increases awareness of the substantial safety precautions already undertaken in CCUS projects. In the local context, the narrative should include the focus on jobs, yet manage expectations to be realistic about the job creation of the project.

When it comes to political development, the discussion confirmed that the development in both regions (the Baltic and the Mediterranean) is in favour of the large-scale deployment of CCS, especially for industries like steel and cement. In countries like Denmark, Germany and Poland, the political landscape vis-à-vis CCS has changed significantly in the positive direction.

Legal, regulatory, and economic issues are interlinked with political development. For example, in Greece a regulatory framework was announced last year and there is some movement in CCS. In Poland a project was cancelled because of lack of financial support from the government, however, the current political development in general is favourable to CCUS. Elections in Poland will be held soon, and it is likely that a new geological and mining law that affects CO₂ storage will be amended favourably. Offshore storage is less challenging in Poland and is allowed everywhere except for protected areas. Also, the European Commission is influencing national conversations through the Net Zero Industry Act. A question remaining unanswered is what happens to countries without offshore

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storage, for example, Austria; this could gain further attention as nations in such a position run out of options when needing to meet EU mandates for CO₂ emissions reductions.

3.3. Key takeaways on socio-political issues

- Trust in governments and industry is generally higher in the Nordic countries compared to the Mediterranean. Oppositions in countries such as France is not necessarily about CC(U)S *per se*, but against the state and financial interests implementing it.
- Trust in research and NGOs is high in both the Baltic Sea and the Mediterranean regions. In countries with low trust in the government, it is more effective if the information about CC(U)S comes from these types of stakeholders.
- One key to good communication is coordination between actors that are collaborating on delivery of a project.
- Early involvement of local communities is important.
- The political development in both regions is in favour of the large-scale deployment of CCS, not least for industries like cement and steel.
- The political landscape vis-a-vis CCS has changed significantly in favour of CCS, as is evident in countries like Germany, Denmark, and Poland.

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